

On a New Method of Preparation of Hexammine-tri-ol-dicobalti-chloride and the Preparation of some Nuclear Polymers.

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Both from our work on the thiosulphato-aquo-tetrammine-cobaltic salts (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 835), and that of Ray on the thio-sulphato-pentammine-cobaltic series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 64) it is apparent that S_2O_3 radicle takes up one co-ordination position only in the cobaltamine complexes.

Attempt was made to introduce S_2O_3 radicle within the complexes of the triammine series. Our starting material was according-

ly the dichrocobaltic salt, $\left[\begin{array}{c} Cl_2 \\ Co(NH_3)_3 \\ H_2O \end{array} \right] Cl$ which was obtained

by the action of concentrated hydrochloric acid on $\left[\begin{array}{c} (NO_2)_3 \\ Co \\ (NH_3)_3 \end{array} \right]$ by

the method of Jørgensen (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 17, 475).

Reaction with sodium thiosulphate gave rise to the decomposition of the complex even at low temperatures with the formation of a very small amount of a red salt which was proved to be tetrahydrated hexammine-tri-ol-dicobalti-thiosulphate. The triammine cobaltic salts are generally very unstable, on the other hand, the condensation product of the triamines, which have very little been studied, are much more stable. Werner obtained a series of brownish red

salts of the formulæ $\left[(NH_3)_3 Co \begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ -OH- \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{OH} \end{array} Co(NH_3)_3 \right] X_3$ by

(A)

careful addition of dilute caustic soda on the dichrocobaltic chloride. The yield as pointed out by him is too small for practical utility and the maximum yield obtained by him is 0.5 g. from 5 g. of the dichrosalt ; cf. E. Birk (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 175, 405) who has also by a modification of Werner's method using caustic potash and excess of ammonium chloride instead of caustic soda been able to increase the yield from 0.5 to 1.8 g.

As regards the mechanism of the formation of the condensation product Werner assumed the following.

If the above mechanism is to be assumed it naturally follows that the hydrolysis and the subsequent removal of the free acid is the prominent factor in bringing about this coupling. Werner, therefore, added the calculated amount of caustic soda very carefully from a burette, the temperature being kept low.

It suggested to us that if we can use a suitable reagent which will favour the hydrolysis and keep the solution at proper p_{H} , better yield of this condensation product would be expected. We, accordingly, used instead of caustic soda, hexamethylenetetramine and have been able thereby to increase the yield from 0.5 g. of Werner to 2.5 g. We have thus found a new method of preparation of the hexammine-tri-ol-dicobalt salts.

From the hexammine-tri-ol-dicobalt salts, which is much more stable than its parent dichro-cobalt salt, by double decomposition with sodium thiosulphate, the hexammine-tri-ol-dicobaltic thiosulphate of the formula (I) is obtained.

By the action of sodium thiosulphate, which is also hydrolysing agent, on dichro-cobalt chloride, a very small amount of red salt was obtained which was found to be identical with the above compound.

By double decomposition of dodecammine-hexol-tetracobaltic nitrate with sodium thiosulphate a black salt of the formula (II) is obtained

which is a co-ordination isomer of the red salt (I).

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EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the hexamine-tri-ol-dicobaltic chloride.—Werner (*Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 2674 ; Werner and Grün, *ibid.*, 1907, **40**, 4884) first prepared the above compound by careful addition of calculated amount of NaOH on dichro-cobalt chloride. The yield obtained by him was only 12·5 p. c. of the theoretical, whereas by the following procedure we obtained 62·5 p. c. of the theoretical yield.

5 G. of the dichloro-aquo-triammine cobaltic chloride (known as the dichro-cobalt-chloride) were moistened with 5 c.c. of water in a small beaker and the mixture was heated over a tiny flame till complete mixing was effected. To the above solution, 1·5 g. of 'urotropine' was added and the temperature was raised to 45° by keeping the mixture for a few minutes on a hot water-bath. It was then removed from the water-bath and quickly filtered under suction. The red thick liquid thus obtained was placed in a freezing mixture of ice and salt. Brownish-red needle shaped crystals were obtained. The yield of the crude product was 2·9 g. This was purified by dissolving in 10 c.c. of water by careful heating on the water-bath. The solution was filtered and absolute alcohol was added drop by drop until turbidity appeared. It was again dissolved to a clear liquid on warming. The filtered solution began to crystallise on cooling, yield 2·5 g. (Found: Co, 29·72 ; NH₃, 25·57 ; Cl, 27·04. [A] Cl₃, H₂O requires Co, 29·83 ; NH₃, 25·79 ; Cl, 26·90 per cent.).

Preparation of hexamine-tri-ol-dicobaltic thiosulphate.—4 G. of the hexamine-tri-ol-dicobaltic chloride were dissolved in 20 c.c. of water and to the clear filtered solution, powdered sodium thiosulphate (4 g.) was added and the whole vigorously stirred. A dull red product was obtained. It was drained, first washed with cold water, then with dilute alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. The yield is 2·5 g. The product is insoluble in water. (Found: Co, 24·69 ; S, 20·33 ; NH₃, 21·3. Formula (I) requires Co, 24·84 ; S, 20·21 ; NH₃, 21·47 per cent.).

Preparation of dodecammine-hexol-tetracobalt-thiosulphate.—Diaquo-tetrammine-cobaltic nitrate obtained from the carbonato-tetrammine salt is acidic in aqueous solution. When it was neutralised with NaOH or KOH and kept in air, shining black crystals of dodecammine-hexol-tetracobaltic nitrate are obtained. Dodecammine-hexol-tetracobalt-nitrate has been prepared by adding pyridine to a hot dilute acetic acid solution of diaquo-tetrammine-cobaltic

nitrate according to the method of Werner (*Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 2103). (Found: Co, 25.93; NH_3 , 22.16. Dodecammine-hexol-tetracobalt-nitrate requires Co, 25.82; NH_3 , 22.32 per cent.).

4.5 G. of dodecammine-hexol-tetracobalt-nitrate were dissolved in 25 c.c. water and 2.5 g. of powdered sodium thiosulphate were added to the solution and stirred. A black crystalline substance was obtained. It was drained, washed first with cold water in which it was almost insoluble and finally with absolute alcohol. The yield was 3 g. (Found: Co, 24.61; S, 20.30; NH_3 , 21.33. Formula (II) requires Co, 24.84; S, 20.21; NH_3 , 21.47 per cent.).

It is interesting to observe that the black crystalline dodecammine-hexol-tetracobalt-thiosulphate and the red crystalline hexamine-tri-ol-dicobaltic thiosulphate are two co-ordination polymers.

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